

SEARCH FOR INSECTICIDES. PART III

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Substituted *www*-trichloroacetophenones have been prepared by the action of trichloroacetyl chloride on certain halogen derivatives of benzene. Resorcinol monomethyl ether and *o*-chloroanisole have been condensed with chloral.

A highly active insecticide usually contains a toxic component and also groups which impart lipid solubility. In previous communications (Sen and Bhargava, this *Journal*, 1948, 26, 278; 1949, 26, 243), the preparation of a number of compounds containing the chlorobenzene nucleus and a $-CCl_3$ group has been described. In this paper, the authors have utilised the Friedel-Crafts reaction and the DDT-type condensation for the preparation of a number of compounds containing the same groupings; in some cases the chlorine atom in the phenyl group has been substituted by other halogens or groupings like $-OCH_3$, whose toxic nature has already been established.

The synthesis of a number of halogen substituted acetophenones (*i.e.* 4-chloro-, *o*-chloro-, 4-*o*-dichloro-, *oo*-dichloro-, 2:4-*o*-trichloro-, *www*-trichloro-, 4-bromo-, *o*-bromo-, *o*-chloro-4-bromo-, *o*-bromo-4-chloro- and 4-*o*-dibromo- acetophenones) by Friedel-Crafts reaction between halogen-substituted acetyl chlorides and halogenated benzenes, has already been described in the literature (Friedel and Crafts, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1884, vi, 1, 507; Gautier, *ibid.*, 1888, vi, 14, 345; Collet, *Compt. rend.*, 1897, 126, 718; Kunckell, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1703; Schweitzer, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 550; Collet, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1897, iii, 17, 69; Klags, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2642; Boesken, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1901, 20, 106). The authors have extended this reaction to chloro-, bromo-, fluoro- and *o*-dichlorobenzenes, the acid chloride used in all cases being trichloroacetyl chloride, and the resulting products obtained being 4-*www*-tetrachloro-, 4-bromo-*www*-trichloro-, 4-fluoro-*www*-trichloro- and 3:4-*www*-pentachloro- acetophenones respectively. In all these reactions, a little excess over one and a half mole of anhydrous aluminium chloride and trichloroacetyl chloride was used. It has been found that in case of fluorobenzene, charring occurs even at 40°. In the case of chloro- and bromobenzenes, complete resinification occurs at 78°, while very little reaction takes place at 0°. The Friedel-Crafts reaction between *o*-dichlorobenzene and trichloroacetyl chloride proceeds smoothly at 78°, a nearly theoretical yield of the product being obtained. No reaction occurs between *p*-dichlorobenzene and trichloroacetyl chloride even after refluxing in petroleum ether solution for 12 hours, unchanged *p*-dichlorobenzene being recovered.

4-*www*-Tetrachloroacetophenone has been previously prepared by Gautier (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1888, vi, 14, 403), who obtained it by the chlorination of 4-*oo*-trichloroacetophenone at 200°. The boiling point of the compound is reported to be 181°/45 mm. and m.p. 28°. We have obtained the compound as a pink liquid solidifying on cooling at room temperature and possessing b.p. 108°-110°/15 mm. This compound and the corresponding bromo and fluoro compounds begin to darken almost immediately after

distillation and assume a permanent dark colour within a short time. No such effect of light was observed on 3:4-*www*-pentachloroacetophenone.

A very large number of compounds of the type of DDT have been prepared by similar condensations in the recent years. The authors have in this paper, also carried out the condensation of chloral with *o*-chloroanisole and monomethyl ether of resorcinol. In both the cases, solid products have been obtained in low yields; these have been provisionally assigned the structure 1:1:1-trichloro-2:2-di-(3'-methoxy-4' chlorophenyl) ethane and 1:1:1-trichloro-2:2-di-(2'-methoxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl) ethane respectively on the basis that in such condensations, the -CHCCl₃ group generally occupies the *para* position to the Cl or OH group.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Halogen-substituted www-Trichloroacetophenones—The halobenzene, dissolved in petrol ether, was taken in a 250 c.c. pyrex flask fitted with a reflux condenser, and anhydrous aluminium chloride (1½ to 2 times the theoretical amount) added. It was then cooled in ice and trichloroacetyl chloride (1½ to 2 times the theoretical amount) added dropwise from the top of the condenser. After 2 hours, the ice-bath was removed and the contents of the flask gradually heated (see Table I). After leaving overnight, the aluminium complex was decomposed by ice and hydrochloric acid. The oil which separated out was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed, dried over fused calcium chloride and filtered. Ether was removed from the filtrate and the residual liquid distilled in vacuum, when the halogen-substituted *www*-trichloroacetophenone corresponding to the halobenzene used, was obtained. The various halogenated *www*-trichloroacetophenones thus prepared are described in Table I. All these ketones solidified in the receiver when cooled with ice and salt, and with the exception of 3:4-*www*-pentachloroacetophenone (on which no action of light was observed), assumed a permanent dark colour after a few hours.

1:1:1-Trichloro-2:2-di-(3'-methoxy-4'-chlorophenyl) ethane.—*o*-Chloroanisole (14.3 g) and concentrated sulphuric acid (40 c.c.) were taken in a 500 c.c. pyrex three-necked flask fitted with a dropping funnel, a reflux condenser and a mechanical stirrer; the flask was then cooled in ice and chloral (7.4 g.) added slowly through the dropping funnel, in the course of 15 minutes. The mixture was stirred for 3 hours in the cold; the temperature of the water-bath was then raised to 70°-80° and stirring continued for another 2 hours. After leaving overnight, it was poured over crushed ice when a red sticky mass separated out. This was allowed to stand, the supernatant aqueous layer was decanted off and the red residue washed several times with cold water. It was then covered with water and left in a refrigerator. After a fortnight it formed a solid lump, which was powdered and left for a few days more, covered with water, in the cold, when an almost colorless solid was obtained. This was filtered and recrystallised from hot dilute alcohol as pale yellow-orange crystals, m.p. 96-97°, yield 5.1 g. (24.9% of theory). (Found: C, 45.91; H, 3.07; Cl, 42.53. C₁₈H₁₃O₂Cl₃ requires C, 46.32; H, 3.14; Cl, 42.82 per cent).

TABLE I

No. Halobenzene used.	Weight of reactants Halo- AlCl_3 , CCl_3COCl , benzene	Temp. & time of reaction.	Yield (% of theory).	B. p	Colour.	Found (%) C. H. Cl	Calculated (%) C. H. Cl
I	Chlorobenzene 5.6 g. 11 g. 14.4 g.	45-50° for 7 hours.	93.4	108°-110°/15mm.	Colorless, turning pink.	36.97 1.51 54.83	37.21 1.55 55.04
II	Bromobenzene 5.2 7.5 10.4	½ hour at 60° and then 4 hours at 50°.	69.9	108°-110°/23 mm	Pale violet, turning deep violet.	30.51 1.38 61.25*	30.73 1.32 61.65*
III	Fluorobenzene 4.8 12 14.4	72 hours at room temp. (26-28°).	74.5	108°/17 mm.	Light green turning deep violet.	39.47 1.59 ...	39.75 1.66 ...
IV	o-Dichlorobenzene 7.4 12 13.7	78° for 5 hours.	95.1	90°/4 mm. or 107°/23	Colorless.	32.67 1.01 ...	32.82 1.02 ...

I = 4-~~chloro~~-Tetrachloroacetophenone ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCl}_4$).II = 4-Bromo-~~chloro~~-trichloroacetophenone ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCl}_3\text{Br}$).III = 4-Fluoro-~~chloro~~-trichloroacetophenone ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCl}_3\text{F}$).IV = 3 : 4-~~chloro~~-Pentachloroacetophenone ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{OCl}_5$).

* Cl+Br

1:1:1-Trichloro-2:2-di-(2'-methoxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl) ethane.—The condensation of monomethyl ether of resorcinol (11 g.) with chloral (6.5 g.) in presence of sulphuric acid (conc., 33 c.c.), was carried out as in the previous experiment. The stirring was carried on for 2 hours at 0°; the contents of the flask were then left overnight and poured over crushed ice (600 g.), when a red crystalline solid separated out. This was allowed to settle in a refrigerator, filtered and washed with a little water. On slow evaporation of a cold alcoholic solution of the compound, a dark red crystalline solid was obtained which did not melt up to 300°, yield 4 g. (23.9% of theory). (Found: C, 50.82; H, 3.96. $C_{18}H_{15}O_4Cl_3$ requires C, 50.86; H, 3.98 per cent).

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